

Schuhleistenkeil (Cham, Heiligkreuz, Inv.- Nr. 2442-24.1)

Processing Report

07 July 2022

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	248	Camera stations:	166
Flying altitude:	18.5 cm	Tie points:	62,388
Ground resolution:	0.0247 mm/pix	Projections:	223,705
Coverage area:	33.1 cm ²	Reprojection error:	0.695 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro ...	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm	No
ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro ...	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm).

ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm)

83 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm
F:	7500		
Cx:	0	B1:	-4.65317
Cy:	0	B2:	3.08607
K1:	0	P1:	-0.000625846
K2:	0	P2:	0.000877949
K3:	0	P3:	0
K4:	0	P4:	0

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm).

ILCE-6000, E 30mm F3.5 Macro (30mm)

83 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	6000 x 4000	30 mm	4 x 4 μm
F:	7500		
Cx:	0	B1:	0.198199
Cy:	0	B2:	-3.01149
K1:	0	P1:	-0.000650291
K2:	0	P2:	0.000909668
K3:	0	P3:	0
K4:	0	P4:	0

Scale Bars

Label	Distance (m)	Error (m)
target 1530_target 1540	0.100003	2.91386e-06
target 1530_target 1550	0.0999971	-2.91119e-06
target 1650_target 1660	0.099974	-2.59769e-05
target 1650_target 1670	0.100026	2.59607e-05
Total		1.84779e-05

Table 2. Control scale bars.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 0.111 mm/pix
Point density: 81.1 points/mm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	248
Aligned cameras	166
Markers	6
Scale bars	4
Coordinate system	Local Coordinates (m)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	62,388 of 158,945
RMS reprojection error	0.11916 (0.694894 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.588399 (26.3854 pix)
Mean key point size	4.7823 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	3.28466
File size	9.87 MB

Depth Maps

Count	161
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Processing time	1 hours 14 minutes
Memory usage	8.41 GB
Date created	2022:05:03 09:00:03
Software version	1.7.1.11797
File size	586.26 MB

Model

Faces	685,396
Vertices	342,700
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	13,000 x 13,000, 4 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Processing time	1 hours 14 minutes
Memory usage	8.41 GB

Reconstruction parameters

Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Depth maps
Interpolation	Disabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	14 minutes 51 seconds
Memory usage	2.92 GB

Texturing parameters

Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Average
Texture size	13,000
Enable hole filling	No
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	45 seconds

UV mapping memory usage	912.00 MB
Blending time	3 minutes 41 seconds
Blending memory usage	5.46 GB
Date created	2022:05:03 09:14:49
Software version	1.7.1.11797
File size	139.10 MB

System

Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.3 build 14331
OS	Linux 64 bit
RAM	3.83 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8265U CPU @ 1.60GHz
GPU(s)	None